

OPPORTUNITIES FOR IMPROVING THE PERFORMANCE EVALUATION OF GENERAL SECONDARY SCHOOL PRINCIPALS

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Abstract: This article highlights tasks of general secondary school principals, involvement of their work. Additionally, it shows some data about the importance of principals in our life to tackle with some problems, and it gives some solutions to help estimate their work effectively.

Keywords: General secondary school principals, school, knowledge, estimate, pupils, promotion, challenges, attention, seminars, conduct lessons.

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A school is essential part of all people in their life. As they gain basic knowledge in this field. Because of this reason, all schools must be well-organized for everyone's needs such as learning how to read, spelling their own name, counting, expressing one's ideas without any problems. If we want to see well-organized schools, the government should work with schools' principals, at first.

Because, principals who control a school's environment, motivate inbuilt children, give a promotion to teachers or staff who could manage their work effectively. However, we must know school principals as managers, they must be teachers, initially.

For this matter, they have to work on yourself to deal with such kind of problems if it exists. Since, they teach other teachers how to organize lessons. They must obtain lots of skills to deal with any kind of problems.

As we know, a school covers average 200 to 300 pupils. The same following lines, all pupils have some people who cares about them. Always, most parents tend to know their kid or child how do their job by calling teachers or school's principals or in person. However, it may appear some problems at school which related to school boys.

At this time, most parents visit principals and make complaint about an issue, sometimes they may ignore true facts about their child. From the above points, it is clear to all of us that the level of educational potential of the future youth of our country depends on the effective performance of general secondary education schools. That is why it is very important to control them.

For this kind of events , all principals should be ready psychologically to do not give their attention. Because, these actions may lead most principals not being effective , some health problems and can be great reason for their sadness. That is to say , they have to be ready all conditions to deal with some difficulties .

As we all know, and for several of the reasons above, being a director of general secondary education highlights many challenges. The director of each general secondary school should be in charge of the literacy of the students in the school, how well the teachers conduct their lessons and how well they know their subjects. At the same time, teachers should be responsible for the organization of additional clubs for each student to use their extra time effectively.

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Now, we will consider with you several ways to evaluate the effectiveness of principals of general secondary schools. There are the following directions for evaluating their effectiveness:

- 1) one day a week to conduct various classes, seminars or trainings for school principals on how to effectively perform their work;
- 2) to motivate them by announcing different nominations or giving different amounts of monetary gains;
- 3) checking the knowledge levels of students and teachers twice a year
- 4) to create a friendly atmosphere between students and school principals in general secondary schools and organize frequent meetings with them.

By this essential four ways , both principals and pupils get benefits. For principals, they can get some promotions or financial benefits what they are doing. Additionally, they can be a great example for other principals to use how their time effectively to develop their school. Looking at pupils , they can obtain more than any principals.

As we said , a school is a primary step for everyone . This step can be a reason of a lot of achievements in the future. If their school is well - organized and principals are good , pupils can get more things from their school. To create this atmosphere, the government should conduct a lot of training for principals to can manage their time effectively and use it too.

As a conclusion, secondary school principals play a huge role in our life . Because they are main part of producing well - educated children for our future . By their work , they help the development of our life . So , it is essential to control what they do . Four given ideas can be suit for controlling their work , and help them to work more effectively.

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